

A Stable Matching Approach to Energy Efficient and Sustainable Serverless Scheduling for the Green Cloud Continuum

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Abstract—Cloud infrastructures are evolving from centralised systems to geographically distributed federations of edge devices, fog nodes, and clouds - often known as the *Cloud-Edge Continuum*. Continuum systems are dynamic, often massive in scale, and feature disparate infrastructure providers and platforms; this greatly increase the complexity of developing and managing applications. The *Serverless* paradigm shows the potential to greatly simplify the process of building Continuum applications - however, current scheduling mechanisms for Serverless Continuum platforms pay little attention to reducing the *energy consumption* and improving the *sustainability* of function execution. This is a significant omission, made worse as computing nodes within a Continuum may be powered by renewable energy sources that are intermittent and unpredictable, making low-powered and bottleneck nodes unavailable.

There is great opportunity to design a decentralized energy management scheme for scheduling Serverless functions that takes advantage of the different layers of the Continuum, such as IoT devices located at the Edge, on-premises clusters closer to the data sources, or directly on large Cloud infrastructures. To achieve this, we formally model a green energy-aware Serverless workload scheduling problem for the multi-provider Cloud-Edge Continuum. We then design *stable matching* based technique for decentralized energy management (utilising a distributed controller) that considers the availability of green energy nodes and the QoS requirements of Serverless functions. We prove the complexity, stability and termination of the proposed heuristic algorithm, and also compare its performance with baseline scheduling techniques.

Keywords- Cloud-Edge Continuum, Serverless Computing, Renewable energy, Scheduling, Function-as-a-Service, Matching.

I. INTRODUCTION

To address the ultra-low latency demands of next generation applications, Cloud infrastructures are rapidly progressing from centralised large-scale systems to geographically distributed federations of edge devices, fog nodes, and cloud data centers - often termed as the *Cloud-Edge Continuum*. The Cloud-Edge Continuum, illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of heterogeneous regions (e.g. R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4) containing many IoT devices (shown by black dots), fog & edge nodes and Cloud data centers (represented by E and C), powered by multiple energy providers (e.g. EP_1, EP_2, EP_3, EP_4), and controlled by different service operators.

Fig. 1. Migrating functions in a Continuum system

To better address the requirements of modern applications, a Continuum system must be capable of managing the massive complexity of disparate infrastructure providers, energy providers, resource heterogeneity, and infrastructural dynamicity, whilst providing secure orchestration over public networks [1]. These characteristics lead to many substantial integration challenges (from both technical and business perspectives) for providers, and introduce further complexity - particularly in

resource scheduling and management across multi-layered and multi-provider infrastructures. More concretely, conventional cloud scheduling policies rely on greedy algorithms that do not effectively manage Cloud-Edge Continuum platform heterogeneity and fail to optimize data transfers.

Serverless computing [2], [3] is a popular emerging paradigm (projected market value expected to reach \$42.4 billion by 2030 [4]) to significantly reduce this complexity for application developers, moving much of the application management burden to providers. Serverless technologies allow developers to implement application functionality as invocable services (often referred to as *Function-as-a-Service (FaaS)*), with providers managing the provisioning, deployment, and scaling of these services based on a range of factors such as cost, load balancing, efficiency, etc. This offers the prospect of greatly improving the ability of smaller developers to implement applications across a complex Continuum of resources.

While this server-agnostic model partially alleviates several Cloud-Edge Continuum characteristics (e.g. providing code-offloading capabilities to constrained devices, removing infrastructural dynamicity concerns for application developers, etc.), there are still multiple distinct research challenges that need to be addressed to build a functional multi-provider Serverless infrastructure for Cloud-Continuum. Crosscutting these challenges is the necessity for Cloud-Edge systems to *adapt* to uncertain nature of end users and providers demands, system and network behaviors, and most importantly, *integrate energy considerations* (e.g. the availability of renewable (green) energy sources, multiple energy providers, energy policies and pricing, the requirement to balance energy consumption over large areas with non-Cloud consumers, etc.) [1], [5].

On a large scale, this adaptability requires energy-aware monitoring and control of the heterogeneous platforms and applications that deal with massive volumes of data, and the deployment of complex software environments such as the ones required for AI/ML applications. The size of Continuum systems is expanding rapidly; forecasts suggest that over 75 billion devices will be deployed in the Continuum by the year

2025 [7]. This leads to Continuum systems requiring massive energy consumption; one estimate suggests that data centers and networks combined will consume 18% of the world’s electrical power consumption by 2030 [8]. This consumption is causing great strain on electricity grids (national and local) [12] and has the potential for significant environmental impact, especially considering that nearly 80% of the world’s energy is still produced by brown energy (non-renewable) sources such as coal, natural gas, oil, and nuclear energy, which emit a very high *carbon footprint* [11].

The carbon footprint of Continuum systems can be estimated by considering the carbon intensity (CI) of the power grids powering each node; this is expressed in grams of CO_2 equivalent per watt ($g\text{-}CO_2eq/kWh$), which reflects the average weighted carbon intensity of the mix of sources utilized to generate energy at any particular moment. Fig. 2 shows the carbon intensity variations of grid energy for two days in four regions of the Europe. These variations *encourage the utilization of temporal and spatial shifting techniques in Cloud systems* [9], as a task’s carbon footprint can vary by up to 4.3 times (for example, notice the CI values for the Netherlands at 3pm and 9pm) depending on whether it is executed during a low or high carbon-intensity period. Moreover, it can be seen that the carbon intensity of grid energy varies by up to 20 times across different regions (for example, the CI value between Sweden and Netherlands at 9pm) [10].

This issue is becoming ever more acute as society’s energy challenges grow; it is a major concern for power grids, which must balance the demands of Continuum systems alongside those of other energy consumers. It is thus crucial to develop methods for mitigating, optimizing and, where feasible, reducing energy consumption in Continuum systems. An encouraging technique is *energy-aware resource scheduling* in Serverless systems; by closely monitoring large federated systems, functions can be placed on the most energy-efficient resource available, considering factors such as Quality of Service (QoS) and pricing, etc. For instance, functions can intentionally be assigned to Continuum nodes that are currently utilizing substantial amounts of *green (renewable) energy*, such as wind or solar power. Conversely, functions can be offloaded away from nodes in regions experiencing high energy demand to free up local power grid capacity for other users, thereby achieving load balancing across regional and national power grids. These scheduling decisions may also consider energy pricing alongside user and software service-level objectives (SLOs). For example, functions demanding ultra-low latency (delay sensitive) may be placed on a local edge node, even if that node relies on energy from a *brown (non-renewable) energy source*, while delay-tolerant functions may be scheduled to more sustainable locations.

An example of one such scenario is shown in Fig. 1. Initially, certain functions f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4 , and f_5 are assigned to region R_2 . However, as green energy availability in R_2 reduces to 10% (suffering from low energy density), an offloading decision is made to transfer functions f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4 and f_5 to well-powered regions R_1 and R_4 , where green energy

Fig. 2. Carbon intensity for four different regions

availability is higher (e.g. 90% at R_1 and 70% at R_4). This strategic offloading of functions enables us to maximize the green energy usage while also balancing resource loadings across federated regions of the Continuum.

However, the current scheduling mechanisms for Serverless platforms *pay little attention to the reduction of energy consumption during function execution - and none adequately integrate energy considerations (e.g. availability of renewable (green) energy sources, multiple providers, energy policies, energy pricing, and the requirement to balance consumption over large areas with other non-Cloud consumers, etc.)*. Energy-aware resource scheduling in Serverless Cloud-Continuum is a particular concern when developing autonomous resource management systems, as current management approaches do not consider energy policies, constraints and optimizations across large federations. To address these research gaps, we make the following key **contributions**:

- *Problem*: Formulate the problem of decentralized energy management for green energy aware Continuum nodes running on Serverless and multi-provider Cloud-Edge Continuum.
- *Research approach*: Presenting a matching theory based research approach to dynamically manage resource allocations to Serverless workloads.
- *Evaluation*: Evaluate the efficiency of proposed solution in comparison with baseline scheduling techniques in terms of green energy usage, workload intensity, throughput, and satisfaction.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the current research status of relevant Serverless-aware Cloud-Edge models. Section III emphasizes on system modeling and problem formulation. Section IV focuses on our research approach for scheduling the Serverless workloads in energy-aware Cloud Continuum. Section V discusses the experimental results, and finally Section VI concludes the paper with future research opportunities in the context of energy-aware Serverless workloads modeling in Cloud-Edge Continuum.

II. RELATED WORK

There is limited research dedicated to energy-aware scheduling for the Serverless Cloud Continuum, and none of it adequately integrates energy considerations. Additionally, few scheduling based solutions have been designed specifically for Serverless Cloud or Edge systems. We discuss some of the most relevant works available in the literature on Scheduling for Serverless Cloud-Edge systems.

Aslanpour et al. [13], [14] discuss the problem of energy-aware scheduling in Serverless edge systems; the authors design several resource scheduling algorithms to assign functions on different edge nodes powered by various green energy and battery energy sources. The objective of the work is to optimize the operational uptime of edge nodes while ensuring a higher Quality of Service (QoS) and throughput. Through experimental evaluation in a real test-bed setup, the authors

demonstrate that their energy-aware scheduler enhances operational uptime, serviceability, and throughput compared to benchmark algorithms. However, the work only applies centralized scheduling within a homogeneous environment, and evaluates energy-efficiency specifically for edge nodes only.

Angelelli et al. [17] investigate the utilization of Serverless platforms within the Cloud Continuum. Their study evaluates the effect of platform heterogeneity during scheduling while optimizing data transfers and function execution times. They develop a multi-objective scheduling policy for the allocation of Serverless functions across Cloud-Edge platforms, with the objectives of minimizing makespan and the data downloads required for deploying containers and functions' I/O operations. The experiments show disparities between greedy and multi-objective scheduling algorithms in Serverless platforms - however, this scheduling policy is time-consuming, and does not take into account delay-sensitive tasks and the energy consumption of edge-cloud nodes.

Rastegar et al. [18] present 'EneX', an energy-aware execution scheduler for Serverless resource providers. The authors investigate online and offline solutions, taking into account key factors such as performance, scalability, and complexity. Russo et al. [20] design a FaaS framework for function offloading and migration in cloud-edge systems, developing various mechanisms for Serverledge FaaS framework and evaluating the approaches in terms of throughput and response time. Dantas et al. [19] design 'GreenLAC', a load balancer and reverse proxy to manage Serverless deployments of edge-core IoT applications. The authors validate the feasibility and performance of the Serverless balancer using a public cloud platform. Suresh et al. [21] apply OpenWhisk to develop an 'FnSched' scheduling policy, which aims to minimize the cost of resources; the authors integrate CPU-shares regulation and a greedy technique. Zuk et al. [22] develop some online node-level scheduling policies; they modify well-known policies such as FIFO (First-In, First-Out), EECT (Earliest Expected Completion Time), and SEPT (Shortest Expected Processing Time) and utilize historical data to reduce cold starts. To enhance latency and cost efficiency, various task placement solutions are also suggested. ActionWhisk [23] aims to reduce cost rather than energy optimization, whilst another study focuses on latency [24], examining the relocation of tasks and functions within a cluster of heterogeneous nodes.

Gu et al. [25] suggest a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) driven strategy for edge environment, which examines the system states and dynamically makes decisions on energy scheduling and service management to reduce the long-term cost. Verma et al. [26] introduce the 'LEASE' framework for resource allocation in Serverless functions supporting various microservices while meeting their deadlines. To optimize scheduling decisions, they propose a priority-based scheme that offloads functions from over-provisioned nodes to under-provisioned nodes. This approach considers the energy expended in the process without neglecting the finishing time of the microservices. Adeppady et al. [27] explore a straightforward threshold-based approach to reduce the energy

consumption of active servers in Serverless edge environment. This method optimally manages different container states while ensuring the target delay of requested services.

Overall, our analysis of existing work highlights the lack of unified systems and methods to integrate multiple infrastructure providers, energy and data policies, resource restrictions, QoS and SLO requirements of end-users, and key energy factors (such as green energy sources, disparate energy providers, Spatial-temporal pricing, energy provider requirements, etc.). To address these research gaps, we model a green energy-aware Serverless workload scheduling problem for the multi-provider Cloud-Edge Continuum.

III. MODELING AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Modeling

Fig. 1 depicts a high-level overview of a decentralized Serverless Cloud-Edge system; we model a Continuum consisting of a federation of regions i.e., edge and cloud nodes with heterogeneous computational power, storage, and networks. CPU speeds may vary across regions, and each region is powered by green energy sources, brown energy sources and energy storage devices (e.g. battery with limited capacity) with different rates of energy generation. Typically, energy demand is high during peak hours of the day and low during off-peak hours. Energy storage devices store green energy when energy demand in a region is low, allowing utilization of stored energy during peak hours instead of relying on brown energy. Compared to traditional Cloud based platforms, scheduling functionalities are distributed and thus every node within a region is able to schedule the execution of incoming requests. This is especially crucial for requests generated at the edge. The request comprises several microservices, and the function executes tasks associated with each microservice. Each region possesses a local controller, which follows the IBM MAPE-K [28] (Monitoring, Analysis, Planning, Execution, and Knowledge) model. The MAPE-K serves as the reference control model for autonomic and distributed self-adaptive systems. It is designed to accurately capture the dynamics of the system and make effective decisions based on the available data and knowledge. Apart from the local controllers (LCs), there exists a global controller (GC) which provides information on all regions deployed in the continuum. Next, we formulate the Continuum model in terms of regional nodes, workload, Serverless functions, and network delay.

Regional nodes: We consider a discretized workload model by considering \mathbb{T} consecutive equal time slots, denoted as $\mathbb{T} = \{t | t \in [0, T], (t+1) - t = \Delta t \text{ seconds}\}$. We assume a set of regions $R = \{r^j | j \in [1, m]\}$ and set of n heterogeneous computing nodes represented as $D = \{d_i^j | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m]\}$ located across m different regions. A local controller, which is not included in D follows the IBM MAPE-K [28] model to perform management of resources. Assuming $G = \{g_{it}^j | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], t \in T, g_{it}^j \geq 0\}$ represent the energy input to node i , which is powered by green energy sources with different rates of energy generation. Energy consumption of nodes during t is represented as

$E = \{e_{it}^j | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], t \in T, e_{it}^j \geq 0\}$. At each region different function invocation requests are generated at varying and sporadic rates. The State of Charge (SoC) and CPU consumption are critical parameters [9], [13] for device d_i^j located in region j . The SoC denotes the available amount of battery charge on computing nodes at different time intervals represented as $S = \{s_{it}^j | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], t \in T, \delta \geq s_{it}^j \geq 0\}$, where δ denotes the maximum level of battery charge. In a wind and solar hybrid system, wind turbines and photovoltaic modules aggregate their outputs to charge the batteries [29]. The overall resource capacity of nodes is measured in MIPS (Million Instruction Per Seconds) and denoted as $Cap = \{cap_{it}^j | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], t \in T, cap_{it}^j \in [0, \gamma]\}$, where γ denotes the maximum capacity of resources. Nodes can host functions if they satisfy the minimum energy threshold $s_{it}^j \geq \zeta$. The availability of a node is expressed as $Y = \{y_t^{i,j} | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], t \in \mathbb{T}, y_t^i \in \{0, 1\}\}$, which means $y_t^{i,j} = 0$ whenever the node is unavailable during t . Mathematically, the status of Continuum nodes across the region is represented as:

$$d_i^j \in D : y_t^{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s_{it}^j \geq \zeta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here the value of SoC s_{it}^j entirely relies on the SoC at the past time period $s_{i(t-1)}^j$, green energy input g_{it}^j , and energy consumption e_{it}^j at t . For all $d_i^j \in D$, The SoC s_{it}^j is formulated by the following equation [13], [15], [16]:

$$\forall d_i^j \in D : s_{it}^{i,j} = \min(\delta, \max(s_{i(t-1)}^j + g_{it}^j - e_{it}^j, 0)) \quad (2)$$

The surplus green energy for regional node i at time slot t is $(s_{i(t-1)}^j + g_{it}^j - e_{it}^j)$. Here SoC may vary between 0 and δ . In cases where the green energy of all nodes is depleted, the brown energy consumption can be calculated as $(e_{it}^j - g_{it}^j + s_{i(t-1)}^j)$. The value of e_{it}^j is computed based on the assigned functions to d_i^j at t . The overall energy consumption [13] for all $d_i^j \in D$ is modeled as:

$$e_{it}^j = \left(\left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^l ((\alpha_t^{i,j,k} + \beta_t^{i,j,k}) \times q_k)}{\Omega} \times v \right) + \left(\sum_{k=1}^l (oe^{k,trans} \times (\kappa_t^{i,j,k} - \alpha_t^{i,j,k})) + \sum_{k=1}^l (oe^{k,recv} \times \beta_t^{i,j,k}) \right) \right) \times \Delta t \quad (3)$$

Eq. 3 considers energy consumption during direct usage and offloading overhead scenarios [13]. Direct usage estimates the occupied resources of a node for each microservice k , the energy consumption is obtained by $\frac{\sum_{k=1}^l ((\alpha_t^{i,j,k} + \beta_t^{i,j,k}) \times q_k)}{\Omega}$ multiplied by power consumption rate v . For the offloading overhead, energy consumption is computed as $\sum_{k=1}^l (oe^{k,trans} \times (\kappa_t^{i,j,k} - \alpha_t^{i,j,k})) + \sum_{k=1}^l (oe^{k,recv} \times \beta_t^{i,j,k})$. The energy consumption by direct usage and offloading overhead is then multiplied by the total length of the time slot Δt .

Workload: The set of microservices is expressed as $B = \{b^k | k \in [1, l]\}$. The workload generated for a collection of microservices at different time intervals across the regions is represented as $\Lambda = \{\lambda_{it}^{j,k}, |i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], k \in [1, l], t \in T, \lambda_{it}^{j,k} \in [0, \lambda_{it}^{j,k} \max]\}$. The $\lambda_{it}^{j,k} \max$ denotes the maximum possible workload that can enter into node i at region j . For execution, each workload comprises a specific amount of processing in Million Instructions (MI) expressed as $\Pi = \{\pi^k, |k \in [1, l], 0 \leq \pi^k \in \mathbb{R}\}$. The local controller determines the amount of workload $\sigma_{it}^{j,k} \leq \lambda_{it}^{j,k}$ that can be processed locally in its region. The remaining part of workload ($\lambda_{it}^{j,k} - \sigma_{it}^{j,k}$) should be offloaded to the nearest region for processing.

Serverless functions: The set of functions is defined as $F = \{f_t^{i,j,k}, |i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], k \in [1, l], t \in T\}$, here functions $f^{i,j,k}$ perform workload execution for the b^k microservice managed by compute node d_i in region j . Each function contains five attributes, i.e., $f^{i,j,k} = \langle f_{type}^{i,j,k}, f_{priority}^{i,j,k}, f_{at}^{i,j,k}, f_d^{i,j,k}, f_q^{i,j,k} \rangle$, where $f_{type}^{i,j,k}$ denotes the function ID to be invoked, $f_{priority}^{i,j,k}$ represents the priority level (high or low), $f_{at}^{i,j,k}$ denotes arrival time, $f_d^{i,j,k}$ represents the deadline, and $f_q^{i,j,k}$ denotes the resource requirement. The required amount of resources for function deployment is determined as $Q = \{q^k | k \in [1, l], q^k \in [0, \Omega]\}$, where q^k is restricted to the node's maximum capacity γ .

To support auto-scaling feature in Serverless, $f^{i,j,k}$ may contain multiple function replicas at time t , restricted at \mathfrak{R} . Multiple replicas will ensure scalability and fault tolerance. Following the replica-level modelling in [13], we set $\Psi = \{\kappa_t^{i,j,k} | i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], k \in [1, l], t \in T, \kappa_t^{i,j,k} \in [0, \mathfrak{R}]\}$ represents the required number of replicas per function. Based on the expected incoming workload, the number of replicas for b^k on d_i^j at t is estimated as $\kappa_t^{i,j,k} = \min\left(\mathfrak{R}, \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_{it}^{j,k} \times \pi^k}{q_k} \right\rceil\right)$, which may receive a value between 0 to \mathfrak{R} . In the case where d_i^j is unavailable at t , then $\kappa_t^{i,j,k}$ becomes 0 (i.e., zero replica). To model the replicas, the F is expanded to $F = \{f_t^{i,j,k,x}, |i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], k \in [1, l], t \in T, x \in [1, \kappa_t^{i,j,k}]\}$, where x represents the x^{th} replica. Replicas of functions can either be assigned to their local node or offloaded to nearby devices as decided by the local controller. Depending on the $s_t^{i,j}$ on d_i^j at t , the local agent determines local and remote function assignments [13] per regional nodes. The local assignments is defined as $A = \{\alpha_t^{i,j,k}, |i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], k \in [1, l], t \in T, \alpha \geq 0\}$ and remote assignments of functions as $B = \{\beta_t^{i,j,k}, |i \in [1, n], j \in [1, m], k \in [1, l], t \in T, \alpha \geq 0\}$. The local agent must ensure that the constraint for local assignment $\alpha_t^{i,j,k}$ of replicas for $f_t^{i,j,k}$ is $\alpha_t^{i,j,k} \leq \kappa_t^{i,j,k}$. Supposing $f_t^{i,j,k,l}$ is offloaded to any candidate node d^p , then a transfer cost for d_i^j and receiving cost d^p are computed. The overhead energy cost [13] per micro-service for $f_t^{i,j,k,l}$ is expressed as $OE = \{oe^{k,w} | k \in [1, l], w \in \{trans, recv\}, oe^{k,w} \in [0, 1]\}$.

Network delay: The following types of workload processing delays can occur on nodes.

(a) *Transmission delay:* The transmission delay, denoted as $C_{i,j,k}^{wi}(t)$, arises while transmitting workloads over a wireless

network. It correlates directly with the network's input workload (i.e., $\lambda_{it}^{j,k}$).

(b) *Local processing delay:* The local processing delay denoted by $C_{i,j,k}^{loc}(t)$ occurs during processing of workloads within a local region. The delay can be computed using the number of active nodes, denoted by $d_{it}^j \in [0, D]$ and the amount of locally processed workload in the region i.e., $\sigma_{it}^{j,k}$, thus expressed as $C_{i,j,k}^{loc}(\sigma_{it}^{j,k}, d_{it}^j)$. As discussed in [29], the M/G/1 mechanism is adopted for queue management of servers. Consequently, the processing delay in a region is derived using the following expression [29]:

$$C_{i,j,k}^{loc}(\sigma_{it}^{j,k}, d_{it}^j) = \frac{\sigma_{it}^{j,k}}{d_{it}^j \cdot \eta - \sigma_{it}^{j,k}} \quad (4)$$

where η signifies the processing capacity of each node.

(c) *Offloading delay:* The offloading delay expressed as $C_{i,j,k}^{off}(t)$ pertains to the transmission delay of a remaining workload to other regions. With congestion intensity denoted by $h_{i,j,k}(t)$, the offloading delay magnitude is determined by the following equation [29]:

$$C_{i,j,k}^{off}(\sigma_{it}^{j,k}, \lambda_{it}^{j,k}, h_{i,j,k}(t)) = (\lambda_{it}^{j,k} - \sigma_{it}^{j,k}) h_{i,j,k}(t) \quad (5)$$

Now, the overall delay cost for the aggregate input workload is determined by summing the three aforementioned delays [29]:

$$C_{i,j,k}^{delay}(\sigma_{it}^{j,k}, \lambda_{it}^{j,k}, h_{i,j,k}(t), d_{it}^j) = C_{i,j,k}^{wi}(\lambda_{it}^{j,k}) + C_{i,j,k}^{loc}(\sigma_{it}^{j,k}, d_{it}^j) + C_{i,j,k}^{off}(\sigma_{it}^{j,k}, \lambda_{it}^{j,k}, h_{i,j,k}(t)) \quad (6)$$

B. Problem Formulation

Based on the system modeling above, we now formulate the Serverless workload scheduling problem to maximize green energy usage throughout a Continuum by dynamically adjusting the distribution of functions among cloud-edge nodes while meeting QoS and resource constraints. This adjustment is necessary to meet sustainability criteria by optimizing Serverless workloads and unequal distribution of power. When the green energy of all nodes is fully utilised, brown energy consumption can be calculated as $(e_{it}^j - g_{it}^j + s_{i(t-1)}^j)$. The primary objective of the global controller is to minimize the usage of brown energy by maximizing the usage of green energy at t time interval. Mathematically, the optimization objective is modeled as:

$$\min \sum_t \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m (\max(e_{it}^j - g_{it}^j + s_{i(t-1)}^j, 0)) \quad (7)$$

Subject to:

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_t^{i,j,k} + \beta_t^{i,j,k} \right) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \kappa_t^{i,j,k} \right) \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, \forall b^k \in B \quad (8)$$

$$\kappa_t^{i,j,k} = y_t^{i,j} \times \min \left(\mathfrak{R}, \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_{it}^{j,k} \times \pi^k}{q_k} \right\rceil \right) \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, \forall d_i^j \in D, \forall b^k \in B \quad (9)$$

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^l ((\alpha_t^{i,j,k} + \beta_t^{i,j,k}) \times q^k) \right) \leq (y_t^{i,j} \times \omega) \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, \forall d_i^j \in D \quad (10)$$

$$f_w^{i,j,k} + f_p^{i,j,k} \leq f_d^{i,j,k} \quad (11)$$

$$SOV(f_t^{i,j,k}, d_i^j) \neq SOV(f_t^{i,j,k}, d^p) \implies f_t^{i,j,k} \times y_t^{i,j} = 0 \quad (12)$$

For any time period t , Eq. 8 ensures that all function replicas are scheduled, while Eq. 9 stipulates that no scheduling of microservices on a node takes place if the node is unavailable. Eq. 10 specifies that the total capacity required for assigned functions must not surpass the maximum available capacity ω of a node, either local or offloaded. Additionally, the incorporation of variable $y_t^{i,j}$ prohibits assignment on unavailable nodes. Eq. 11 ensures that the expected maximum time to finish function execution must not violate the deadline. Here $f_w^{i,j,k}$ is the waiting time for scheduling the function and $f_p^{i,j,k}$ is the processing time for function. Eq. 12 guarantees that functions assigned to any node possess full authority and autonomy over their resources. A functions cannot be assigned to a node in a region that does not respect its sovereignty (SOV). Maintaining data sovereignty ensures that data is stored and processed in accordance with regulatory mandates throughout the Continuum. We suggest viewing data sovereignty as a collection of constraints [6] (e.g., regional whitelists, lists of excluded nodes/providers, etc.) to be integrated by the controller.

However, the Serverless workload scheduling problem is not solvable in polynomial time due to its NP-hard nature. Therefore, we propose a novel stable matching based solution, as it offers an advantage by providing an approximate solution to this highly complex combinatorial optimization problem. The stable matching problem is a generalisation of the stable marriage problem treated in [33].

IV. STABLE MATCHING FOR SERVERLESS WORKLOAD SCHEDULING

The formulated problem can be cast as the generalized assignment problem [31] such as a bin-packing problem [32] for which we can drive a promising solution by applying matching theory [30], [31]. Specifically, one function is only assigned to one node, while one node can host many functions depending on its available resources. By mapping this problem with matching theory [33], functions and nodes can be treated as the two sides of players involved in a *many-to-one matching* game. This matching idea is widely used in different types of applications such as VM allocation in cloud data centers to obtain the stable assignments [34], [35]. Therefore, we propose an algorithm inspired by the matching theory idea.

A. Construction of Preference Lists

Function's preference list: Each function $f^{i,j,k}$ has a choice to match with any node in a region. However, since a function is concerned with energy benefit and QoS factors,

it builds a preference order $P_f(t)$ over the set of all available nodes applying the following relation:

$$(d_i^{p,j}(SoC, QoS)) \succ_f (d_i^j(SoC, QoS)) \quad (13)$$

These preferences ensure the desirability of more sustainably powered nodes (energy-benefit) and avoid recurring replacements and deadline violations (QoS).

Node's preference list: Similarly, each node constructs a preference list over functions. This preference list is created according to the consolidation policy, in which each node prioritizes improving resource usage by hosting more functions. More specifically, a node d_i^j prefers to be allocated more functions to avoid resource wastage. Therefore, we apply the Best Fit algorithm [32] to build the preference list. We apply the norm-based metric [37] to locate a node with the most suitable resources.

$$f \succ_d f' \Leftrightarrow \sum_{q \in Q} \tau_q (f_q - cap_q^q)^2 < \tau_q (f'_q - cap_q^q)^2 \quad (14)$$

Here, τ_q represents the weight of resource type q .

B. Properties for Matching

Multiple functions can be assigned to one node based on preference functions and matching constraints. To understand the concepts of matching theory, we discuss the following properties:

Matching Function: For a given set of functions F and a set of nodes D , a matching function can be defined formally as $\mu: F \cup D \Rightarrow 2^{F \cup D}$ such that:

- $\mu(d) \subseteq F$ such that $|\mu(d)|^q \leq cap_d^q, \forall d \in D$, where $|\mu(d)|$ represents the aggregated resources of all functions that are matched to d .
- $\mu(f) \subseteq D$ such that $|\mu(f)|^q = cap_f^q$, or $|\mu(f)|^q = 0, \forall f \in F$ and $d \in D$, where $|\mu(f)|^q$ is the node resources of d that is matched to f and $|\mu(f)|^q = 0$ means that function f is not assigned.
- $f \in \mu(d)$ if and only if $\mu(f) = d, \forall f \in F$ and $d \in D$,

These matching properties are defined to be a *many-to-one* relation, where each regional node is matched to a subset of functions. The primary goal of a matching driven solution is to obtain an efficient and stable matching. In this matching game, each participating player specifies their preferences over the others based on their objectives in the Cloud-Edge Continuum.

Blocking Pair: A matching μ can be blocked by an agents' pair (f, d) if there exists a (f, d) pair where $f \notin \mu(d)$ and $d \notin \mu(f)$. Such a pair is termed a blocking pair.

Stable: The obtained matching μ is considered stable if (a) no blocking pairs exist and (b) all functions are allocated to Continuum nodes.

C. Matching based Function Scheduling

At each region, the function invocation requests are submitted to the local controller. If the region has not sufficient energy for function execution, then the global controller is notified. The allocation of functions requests to a node is

Algorithm 1: Matching based Function Scheduling

```
1 Input: Set of regions, set of nodes with respective
   resource capacities, set of functions with their
   required resource capacities,
2 Output: A stable matching  $\mu$  of functions and nodes
3 while  $t \leq T$  do
4   Phase 1: Initialization:
5   /* Regions */
6    $R \leftarrow \{R | r_t^{i,j,k} \in R, r_t^i = \psi\}$ 
7   /* Nodes */
8    $D \leftarrow \{D | d_i^j \in D, i = null\}$ 
9   /* Resource Capacities */
10   $Cap \leftarrow \{Cap | cap_{it}^j \in cap, cap_{it}^j = \gamma\}$ 
11  /* State of Charge */
12   $S \leftarrow \{S | s_{it}^j \in S, s_{it}^j = current\ SoC\}$ 
13  /* Functions */
14   $F \leftarrow \{F | f_t^{i,j,k} \in F, k = null\}$ 
15  Phase 2: Preference List Construction:
16  /* Creating a function's preference list */
17  for each function  $f_t^{i,j,k} \in F$  do
18    1. Find the candidate node  $d_i^{pj}$  such that
        $(d_i^{pj}(SoC, QoS)) \succ_f (d_i^j(SoC, QoS))$ ;
19    2. Add  $d_i^{pj}$  into the preference list of node
        $f_t^{i,j,k}$ .
20  end
21  /* Creating a node's preference list */
22  for each node  $d_i^j \in D$  do
23    1. Find the next function  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  such that
        $cap_{it}^{jq} \geq f_{qt}^{i,j,k}, \forall q \in Q$  and  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  releases the
       least amount of resources;
24    2. Add  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  into the preference list of node  $d_i^j$ .
25  end
26  Phase 3: Matching:
27  while  $\exists f_t^{i,j,k} \in F$  is not placed do
28     $d_i^j \leftarrow$  Find the top rank in  $P(f_t^{i,j,k})$ ;
29    if  $cap_{it}^{jq} \geq f_{qt}^{i,j,k}, \forall q \in Q$  then
30      Assign  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  to  $d_i^j$ ;
31       $cap_{it}^{jq} = cap_{it}^{jq} - f_{qt}^{i,j,k}, \forall q \in Q$ ;
32    end
33    else
34      Determine all  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  to satisfy
        $f_t^{i,j,k} \succ_d f_t^{i,j,k}$ ;
35      Reject all  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  and mark  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  as
       unengaged;
36      Update node  $d_i^j$  resources as:
37       $cap_{it}^{jq} = cap_{it}^{jq} + f_{qt}^{i,j,k}, \forall q \in Q$ 
38      Eliminate  $f_t^{i,j,k}$  out of  $P(d_i^j)$ ;
39      Eliminate  $d_i^j$  out of  $P(f_t^{i,j,k})$ ;
40    end
41  end
42 end
```

performed by the local controller, based on the features of the functions, energy and QoS availability of nodes in the region provided it through the monitoring component of MAPE-K model. Now we discuss our proposed algorithm, as shown in Algorithm 1, which is a generalisation of the *Gale* and *Shapley's* Deferred Acceptance Algorithm (DAA) [33] for many-to-one stable matching for two-sided matching markets. We execute Algorithm 1 on each local agent. In the *Initialization* phase, the local controller collects the current list of functions with their respective resource demands and QoS, as well as the list of nodes along with their resource availability, latest SoC values. In the *Preference List Construction* phase, we create function's preference list and node's preference list. In the function's preference list, each function's replica $f^{i,j,k,l}$ prefers to be located in the node that has better SoC and satisfies its resource constraints and desired QoS levels. Similarly, in the node's preference list, each node builds a preference list over functions. This preference list is created according to the consolidation policy, in which each node prioritizes enhancing resource utilization by deploying more functions. Additionally, it implies that the node favors assignment over unassignment. The *Matching* phase is inspired by the deferred acceptance algorithm [33]. The matching procedure commences from some unassigned functions $f_t^{i,j,k}$. The function $f_t^{i,j,k}$ selects the highest rank node d_i^j from its preference list $P(f_t^{i,j,k})$ to propose. If node d_i^j has enough resources to place function $f_t^{i,j,k}$, it will accept the function $f_t^{i,j,k}$. However, if node d_i^j lacks the necessary resources, it rejects $f_t^{i,j,k}$. Before rejecting $f_t^{i,j,k}$, node d_i^j rejects all its matched functions $f_t^{i',j',k}$ such that $f_t^{i,j,k}$ is preferred over $f_t^{i',j',k}$ (i.e., $(f_t^{i,j,k}) \succ_d (f_t^{i',j',k})$). Subsequently, function $f_t^{i,j,k}$ removes node d_i^j from its preference list $P(f_t^{i,j,k})$ and restarts the proposing process. Consequently, the algorithm can eventually converge to a stable assignment of functions and nodes within a finite number of steps.

D. Distributed Algorithm for Function Offloading

The distributed algorithm for function offloading (shown in Algorithm 2) is a generalisation of the distributed stable matching problem [36]. The distributed algorithm operates in the following phases:

The Local_Controller() procedure: This procedure is executed by every local controller.

- 1) Firstly, in line 5 – 7 it initializes the Function-Priority-List and the Deadline-Based-Priority-List for the region r^j using $f_{priority}^{i,j,k}$ and $f_d^{i,j,k}$ respectively. After that it builds an Offload-List of functions based on Function-Priority-List and Deadline-Based-Priority-List.
- 2) It iteratively applies the constraints until the *Offload-List* becomes empty. From line 10 – 11 it checks the deadline, priority, and available green energy in a local region. If it is satisfied, then it sends an offload message for function $f^{i,j,k}$ to the global controller and waits for a reply.
- 3) From line 12–20, if the reply is *accepted* then it offloads the function $f^{i,j,k}$ and removes the function from the

Algorithm 2: Distributed Algorithm for Function Offloading

```
1 Procedure Local_Controller():
2 Input: Functions which are ready to offload
3 Output: Offloading decision for each function in
  region
4 begin
5   Build an Function-Priority-List in which we rank
  the functions in the region  $r^j$  using  $f_{priority}^{i,j,k}$ 
6   Build a Deadline-Based-Priority-List in which we
  rank the functions in the region  $r^j$  using  $f_d^{i,j,k}$ 
7   Build a Offload-List of functions based on
  Function-Priority-List, and
  Deadline-Based-Priority-List
8   while Offload-List  $\neq \emptyset$  do
9      $f^{i,j,k} \leftarrow$  first element of Offload-List
10    if  $(f_w^{i,j,k} + f_p^{i,j,k} > f_d^{i,j,k})$  or  $f_{priority}^{i,j,k} = high$ 
    and  $s_{it}^j < \zeta$  then
11      sendMsg(offload,  $f^{i,j,k}$ )
12      msg  $\leftarrow$  getMsg()
13      switch msg.type do
14        accepted: Offloading the function  $f^{i,j,k}$ 
15        rejected: if  $(f_w^{i,j,k} + f_p^{i,j,k} > f_d^{i,j,k})$  or
           $f_{priority}^{i,j,k} = high$  and  $s_{it}^j < \zeta$  then
16          Execute the function locally using the
          brown energy.
17        else
18          Defer the execution of function for  $\Delta\theta$ 
          time period.
19      Remove function  $f^{i,j,k}$  from Offload-List
20 end
21 Procedure Global_Controller():
22 Input: Set of available regions and nodes.
23 Output: Offloading decision for each of the function
  in region
24 begin
25   stop  $\leftarrow$  false
26   while  $\neg$  stop do
27     msg  $\leftarrow$  getMsg()
28     switch msg.type do
29       offload:  $f^{i,j,k} \leftarrow$  msg.function
30       if  $SOV(f_t^{i,j,k}, r^j) = SOV(f_t^{i,j,k}, r^{jp})$  and
         $s_{it}^j \geq \zeta$  and  $(f_w^{i,j,k} + f_p^{i,j,k} \leq f_d^{i,j,k})$  then
31         sendMsg(accepted)
32       else
33         sendMsg(rejected)
34       stop: stop  $\leftarrow$  true
35 end
```

Offload-List. If the reply is *rejected* then it executes the function locally using brown energy and removes the function from the *Offload-List*, else it defers the execution of function for $\Delta\theta$ time period until energy becomes available.

4) If the *Offload-List* becomes empty then a stop message is received.

The Global_Controller() procedure: This procedure is executed by the global controller

- 1) Wait for messages from local controller.
- 2) In line 25 – 35, it receives the message from the local controller and checks the sovereignty, SoC, and completion time constraints; if it is satisfied, it sends an “accepted message” else it sends a “rejected message” to the local agent for $f^{i,j,k}$.
- 3) Upon completing the procedure, a stop message is received.

E. Algorithmic Analysis

In this section, we discuss the complexity of the proposed algorithms.

Theorem 1. *The time complexity of the scheduling algorithm Algorithm 1 is $O(FD(F \log_2 D + F \log_2 F))$.*

Proof. : The complexity of the scheduling approach relies solely on the preference lists. For the function’s preference lists, the sorting operation for each function requires a complexity of $O(D \log_2 D)$. Therefore, the overall complexity to construct function preference lists is $O(FD \log_2 D)$ for the set F of functions. Similarly, to build a node’s preference list, the complexity is $O(DF \log_2 F)$. Thus, the overall time complexity of Algorithm 1 is $O(FD(F \log_2 D + F \log_2 F))$. \square

Theorem 2. *The time complexity of the offloading algorithm Algorithm 2 is $O(F \ln F)$.*

Proof. : We provide various functions as input to the algorithm and receive decisions (e.g., offloading, local execution, or rejection) for each function. The overall time complexity of the offloading algorithm is $O(F \ln F)$, where F represents the total number of functions. This is computed as the sum of the number of functions available in the region. \square

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

We validate the efficacy of our proposed algorithm on simulated environments and compared with other baseline approaches.

A. Experimental Settings

We implement the algorithms on a machine with the following specifications: an Intel Core i7-12700 CPU running at 2.1 GHz with 12 cores and 32GB of RAM. We use the Java programming language, running on the OpenJDK Runtime Environment. To evaluate the performance of the algorithms in real-world settings, we assume a Continuum environment with four regions, where edge devices (e.g., Raspberry Pi model 3B+ and Raspberry Pi model 3B) and cloud servers (based

on configurations from Google cluster traces [38]) are used. We randomly generate nodes D ranging from 50 to 100 per region, with the number of microservices per node varying from 1 to 10, executing real-world traces from Wikipedia [40] (for request arrival patterns) and Azure function traces [41] (for resource requirement and average execution times). These traces generate the load for 140 different application types, with a peak load of 16 times the number of requests per second. We use solar energy traces [39] to set the value of G . Each regional node receives different rates of energy input, and the maximum battery capacity is set to 1250 mWh. In the scalability analysis, we study the effect of varying battery sizes. The send and receive overhead values for function offloading are set to 0.02 and 0.01, as described in [13]. The study does not include an analysis of the impact of container startup delays. We conducted each experiment over a one-hour duration and repeated each experiment three times.

B. Baseline algorithms

We compare the performance of our proposed algorithm against the following baseline algorithms described in [13]:

Local: This baseline always deploys functions locally, e.g., $f_t^{i,j,k,l} \rightarrow d_i^j$. This is crucial to understanding the effect of computation offloading.

Random: This baseline randomly places functions across the region. It showcases the worst-case setting, where the scheduler’s decision is made without any intelligence,

First-Fit: This baseline assigns nodes to functions based on their arrival order, allocating them to the first available node that meets their requirements.

C. Performance Metrics

Satisfaction analysis: The satisfaction metric measures the effectiveness of conflict resolution between functions and regional nodes through stable matching. We determine the “satisfaction” of a match by considering the rank percentile of the selected partner (e.g., function or regional node). For regional nodes, satisfaction is determined by the average rank achieved across the matched functions. We assess the performance of satisfaction by varying the total number of functions and regional nodes.

Request filtering: The objective of the request filtering metric is to reduce the number of offloading requests that fail to meet deadline constraints, thereby enhancing the latency of offloading decision-making. We also analyze the impact of various load-input data ratios (LDRs) on the filtering of requests.

Throughput: Throughput measures the aggregated number of functions executed per second. Throughput time is influenced by multiple factors including network congestion and processing power. A higher optimization rate of the algorithm results in faster throughput.

Green energy availability: This metric is defined as the percentage of time in which a node has enough battery charge to execute functions. It measures the availability and sustainability of regional nodes to meet the operational needs of functions.

D. Evaluation Results

Satisfaction analysis: Figures 3(a) and 3(b) illustrate the satisfaction percentages of functions and regional nodes respectively. In this experiment, we examine 50 nodes and increase the functions from 50 to 300. Matching satisfaction is evaluated using the average rank of matches for functions and nodes. Compared to the First-Fit benchmark algorithm, the proposed distributed matching heuristic significantly enhances node performance, effectively resolving conflicts between functions and regional nodes using stable matching. Unlike First-Fit, which only allows a uniform ranking of functions for all listed nodes, this approach enables regional nodes to express their preferences. Additionally, First-Fit cannot match a function to a node with insufficient capacity, resulting in no further rejections from nodes. In contrast, our algorithm allows rejections if a function is more preferable than other node’s functions throughout its execution, thus improving function and node satisfaction. For large-scale simulations, we vary the number of functions and nodes, and analyze overall satisfaction performance. As shown in Fig. 3(c), functions receive their top 6 to 8% preferences, while regional nodes obtain their 12 to 18% preferences, demonstrating that our approach effectively analyzes policies and resolves conflicts for large-scale scenarios.

Request filtering: Request filtering primarily aims to reject offloading requests that cannot meet energy availability, request priority, and deadline constraints, thus minimizing overall delay in decision making. In Fig. 3(d), we analyze the request filtering effect by varying the offloading requests from 100 to 900. From Fig. 3(d), it is evident that the filtering process performs better when the LDR (Local Execution to offloading Delay Ratio) value is low (LDR=1.0), as most offloading request are communication-intensive and suitable for local execution due to time constraints. Thus, in each scenario, it is noticeable that with a high LDR value (LDR=1.5), requests are more likely to be offloaded due to their computation-intensive nature.

Throughput vs. battery size of nodes: Fig. 3(e) analyzes the throughput for different battery size of nodes. The analysis shows a linear growth with larger batteries, as low-powered nodes can remain available for longer periods offering continuous execution of requests. Conversely, the local and random approaches show the least improvement. It is also observed that, if we increase the battery sizes then not only well-powered and under utilized nodes, but also moderately-powered nodes, can store more energy during peak times.

Throughput vs. workload intensity: Fig. 3(f) analyzes throughput for different workload intensities. The graph shows an increasing trend with the rise in workload intensity (i.e., 25% to 100%). A crucial observation is the amplified variance in throughput between different schedulers as workload intensity increases. *This demonstrates the importance of a green energy-aware dynamic scheduler to address demanding workloads effectively.* Although the local scheduler consistently delivers a reasonable throughput, it lacks in meeting sustainability metrics.

Fig. 3. (a) Function satisfaction analysis; (b) Node satisfaction analysis; (c) Overall satisfaction analysis; (d) Request filtering analysis; (e) Battery size of nodes vs. throughput; (f) Workload intensity vs. throughput

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we analyze green energy-aware Serverless workload scheduling for the multi-provider Cloud Continuum. We have formulated a brown energy minimization problem and proposed a stable matching based distributed algorithms to solve it. Through extensive theoretical and experimental analysis, we have shown the efficacy of our proposed method in terms of function and node satisfaction, green energy usage, workload intensity and throughput. Moreover, we compare our implementation with other baseline methods. In the future, we plan to validate the scalability of our approaches by testing temporal and stochastic properties on physical test-beds, likely implemented with Serverless runtimes developed as part of the SovereignEdge.COGNIT project [1].

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